

Study of Role of Vestibular Rehabilitation Programme in Benign Paroxysmal Positional Vertigo

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Abstract:

Background: Benign paroxysmal positional vertigo (BPPV) is a common cause of vertigo and the cause of approximately 20% of all dizziness. In this study we provide an overview of role of vestibular rehabilitation Programme in BPPV.

Aims and Objectives: (1). To evaluate efficacy of particle repositioning maneuver (Epley's Maneuver) in benign paroxysmal positional vertigo. (2). To evaluate efficacy of adaptation/domiciliary habituation exercises (Semont's maneuver, and Brandt – Daroff exercises) in benign paroxysmal positional vertigo.

Keywords: Benign paroxysmal positional vertigo, Exercise, Dizziness.

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Introduction

Benign paroxysmal positional vertigo (BPPV): It is characterized by vertigo when the head is placed in a certain position. Disease is caused by a disorder of semicircular canals. It has been demonstrated that otoconial debris, consisting of crystals of calcium carbonate, is released from the degenerating macula of the utricle and floats freely in the endolymph. When it settles on the cupula of posterior semicircular canal in a critical head position, it causes displacement of the cupula and vertigo which lasts for approximately for 30 seconds. The vertigo is fatigable on assuming the same position repeatedly due to dispersal of the otoconia but can be induced again after a period of rest.

Diagnosis of BPPV: Dix- Hallpike manoeuvre (posterior canal BPPV).

- Brief Latency (1-5 seconds)
- Limited duration (<39 seconds)
- Torsional nystagmus toward lower most ear
- Reversal of nystagmus in sitting position
- Fatigability of the response
- Subjective BPPV
- Classic vertigo during positioning
- No nystagmus seen- repositioning maneuvers still are effective

Vestibular Function Test: BPPV is usually a self-remitting disorder and may resolve as time goes on without specific treatment. Diagnosis of BPPV is based upon vestibular function test. Assessment of vestibular functions can be divided into two groups:

1. Clinical Tests: Romberg test, Untenberger test, Fukuda stepping test, Head shaking test, Caloric test, Timed –up and Go test,

Dix-Halpike test - posterior semicircular canal BPPV, anterior semicircular canal BPPV

Supine - Roll test - horizontal semicircular canal BPPV

2. Laboratory Tests: Electronystagmography, Vestibular Evoked Myogenic Potentials

Management of BPPV

Vestibular rehabilitation: In 1946's, Cooksey[8] analyzed, Cawthorne[5] proposed the use of exercises – vestibular rehabilitation. It was based on a series of eye, head and body movements, in the positions in which the rotational dizziness was triggered. As a therapeutic approach, vestibular exercises bring an improvement in global balance, quality of life, restoring physiological conditions. Besides these mechanisms, there was adaptation, habituation and substitution which were later modified. The Brandt-Daroff exercises are usually indicated in cases of less intense BPPV, as a co-adjuvant to the Epley and Semont maneuvers.

The most popular methods for treating PC-BPPV are

1. Semont's liberatory maneuvers.
2. Epley' maneuvers.
3. Brandt-Daroff Exercise.

Semont's Liberatory manoeuvre: In 1988, Semont.et.al [9]. Described the “liberatory

manoeuvre” based on the cupulolithiasis theory. It was believed that this series of rapid changes of head position freed deposits that were attached to the cupula. The manoeuvre begins with the patient in the sitting position and the head turned away from the affected side. The patient is then quickly put into a position lying on his or her side, toward the affected side, with his or her head turned upward.

After about 5 minutes, the patient is quickly moved back through the sitting position to the opposite position lying on his or her side with his or her head now facing downward. The patient remains in this second position for 5–10 minutes before slowly being brought back to the sitting position (fig.1).

Figure 1: Semont Liberatory manoeuvre (right ear)

Semont and colleagues found an 84% response rate after 1 procedure and a 93% response rate after a second procedure 1 week later.

The liberatory manoeuvre is effective, but is cumbersome with elderly and obese patients.

Epley’s maneuvers (PRM): Epley[10] published his first report on the “canalith repositioning procedure” (CRP). “Epley’s manoeuvre” is performed with the patient sedated[11]. Modified CRP is the particle repositioning manoeuvre (PRM) which is a 3-position manoeuvre that eliminates the need for sedation and mastoid vibration (Fig. 1).

Figure 2: Particle repositioning manoeuvre (right ear)

The patient is seated on a table as viewed from the right side (A). The remaining parts show the sequential head and body positions of a patient lying down as viewed from the top. Before moving the patient into position B, turn the head 45° to the

side being treated (in this case it would be the right side). Patient in normal Dix–Hallpike head-hanging position (B). Particles gravitate in an ampullofugal direction and induce utriculofugal cupular displacement and subsequent counter clockwise

rotatory nystagmus. This position is maintained for 1–2 minutes. The patient's head is then rotated toward the opposite side with the neck in full extension through position C and into position D in a steady motion by rolling the patient onto the opposite lateral side. The change from position B to D should take no longer than 3–5 seconds. Particles continue gravitating in an ampullofugal direction through the common crus into the utricle. The patient's eyes are immediately observed for nystagmus. Position D is maintained for another 1–2 minutes, and then the patient sits back up to

position A. PRM take less than 5 minutes to complete. Patients are then typically asked to remain upright for the next 24–48 hours in order to allow the otoliths to settle, so as to prevent a recurrence of the BPPV. Epley's maneuver is the only recommended method of treating PC-BPPV.

Brandt-Daroff Exercise: Irrespective of the involved canals, the Brandt-Daroff exercise [7] may be attempted when the repositioning maneuvers fail or if patients cannot tolerate the repositioning maneuvers (Figure. 3).

Figure 3: Brandt-Daroff exercise

During its execution, the patient is seating down and turning his head in up to 45° towards the side which does not cause vertigo, and lies down towards the side that causes the symptoms, remaining in this position for 30 seconds, or until vertigo ends; after this time, the patient should seat again, for 30 seconds. Following that the patient lies down again to the opposite side and remains there for 30 seconds more, until returning to the seated position. The exercise duration and frequency depend on neurotological findings.

Methods and Materials

We studied 30 patients who visited the dept. of Otorhinolaryngology in Kurnool Medical College and Hospital with complains of vertigo during a period (JUNE 2023-JUNE 2024) of ONE year.

Results

Epley's maneuver was administered on 30 patients. Out of 30 patients, 17 got instant relief from vertigo and remaining 13 patients did not get any instant relief from vertigo.

All the patients were later given domiciliary exercises (either Semont or Brandt-Daroff) to practice at home, three times in a day and 10 cycles each time.

The 17 instant relief patients were given Semont exercise and Brandt-Daroff exercise. The 13 non-instant relief patients were given Semont exercise and Brandt-Daroff exercise.

Follow up results of instant relief patients were as follows.

The patients who did Semont exercise and Brandt-daroff exercise the results, at 1st follow-up were as

follows 13 pts got relief from vertigo 4 pts didn't get relief. As shown in fig.4.

Figure 4: Results of instant relief group at 1st Follow-up

The patients of instant relief group the results at 2nd follow-up, 14 pts got recovery and 3 pt didn't get relief.

Figure 5: Results of instant relief group at 2nd Follow-up

At 3rd follow-up 17 patients from instant relief group got resolution from vertigo. as shown in fig 6.

Figure 6: Results of instant relief group at 3rd Follow-up

13 non- instant relief patients were given Semont exercise and Brandt- Daroff exercise. Follow up results of non-instant relief patients were as follows. The patients who did Semont and Brandt daroff exercise the results, at 1st follow-up were as follows 9 pts got relief from vertigo 4 pts didn't get relief. As shown in fig.7.

Figure 7: Results of non-instant relief group at 1st follow-up

The non-instant group of patients who practiced Semont and Brandt daroff exercise the results at 2nd follow-up, all 12 pts got recovery and 1 pts didn't get recovery as shown in fig 8.

Figure 8: Results of non-Instant relief group at 2nd follow-up

Non instant group at 3rd follow-up, pts who practiced Semont and Brandt-Daroff exercise all 12 pts got resolution from vertigo and 1 pt didn't get relief from vertigo at 3rd follow-up as shown in fig 9.

Figure 9: Results of non-Instant relief group at 3rd follow-up

Discussion

In the present study 30 cases of unilateral posterior semicircular canal BPPV were taken to evaluate efficacy of vestibular rehabilitation exercises. BPPV is more common in the elderly. This condition seems to have a predilection for the older population. In our study, of the mean age was 55 years of age 40-70yrs among participants correlating with the study of Baloh. et. al., Marciano. et. al.

In the present study results, it was seen that 17(56.66%) out of 30 patients got instant relief from vertigo and the remaining 13(43.33%) patients did not get any relief after administering PRM (Epley's). This showed that PRM is effective in more than 50% of patients to get relief from BPPV at OPD based PRM was done. Ciniglio Apiani. et. al. also conducted a trial using Epley's procedure and reported 26 of 30 (87%) patients were cured. Their two day follow-up included re-evaluation with the Dix-Hallpike manoeuvre.

In study of Herdman.et.al¹⁵ found up to 92% of patients reported benefit after the first follow-up period of one week. In a randomised study, 90% of patients were either improved after a single session with either Semont's or Epley maneuver. Epley [10] himself reported a success rate of more than 90% following a single treatment session. 72% recovered from vertigo immediately after the Epley maneuver 92% patients recovered from vertigo at first week of follow-up. The remaining 2 patients recovered from vertigo during second and third follow-up visits.

Secondary objective of the study was to evaluate the efficacy of domiciliary exercises in benign paroxysmal positional vertigo. In this study patients were given Semont and Brandt- daroff exercises as domiciliary exercises and was followed up three

times. At the end of third follow up 29 patients got relief and 1 patient didn't get relief. This failure could be attributed to (i) non-compliance with the regular exercise protocol, or (ii) Lack of supportive attendants at home, or (iii) Atypical BPPV, or (iv) multicanal pathology which may require further evaluation.

A review of the literature in the study of Soto Varela et. al. comparatively analyzed a total of 106 BPPV patients randomly assigned to receive Brandt-Daroff habituation exercises, Semont maneuver, or Epley maneuver. At the 1-week follow-up, similar cure rates were obtained with the Semont and Epley maneuvers (74% and 71%, respectively), both cure rates being significantly higher than that obtained with Brandt-Daroff exercises (24%). At 3-month follow-up, the cure rate for the Brandt-Daroff exercises increased significantly

Richard et. al. assessed the efficacy of the Epley manoeuvre in a study of 81 patients with posterior semicircular canal BPPV. A group of 61 patients underwent the manoeuvre, while a control group of 20 patients received no therapy .all the patients were evaluated at 1 and 6 months. The percentage of patients who experienced subjective improvement was significantly higher in the treatment group at 1 month (89% vs. 10%) and 6 months (92% vs. 50%) 3 pts in the treatment group who did not improve after treatment underwent a second manoeuvre, and all achieved a positive result. The results of this study support our study regarding the efficacy of Epley maneuver.

Conclusion

Benign paroxysmal positional vertigo is most common disorder of inner ear's vestibular system which is a vital part of maintaining balance. Our

study has shown that use of the three methods may be applied in the management of BPPV with good results. Nevertheless, as BPPV is a common problem more studies must be conducted for more details.

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